

THE STATE OF HEALTH CARE IN NAVOI REGION IN THE PRE-INDEPENDENCE PERIOD

Abstract:

In this article, the state of health care in the region, starting from the processes of the establishment of Navoi region and on the eve of independence, its role in the social development of the region, since 1982, that is, the creation of Navoi region as part of the Uzbekistan Soviet Socialist Republic (UzSSR), and the history of health care, like all other sectors, in order to improve the health of the population, opinions were expressed about the activities of the government and specialists in the development of the medical field, the problems in the health sector and the tasks carried out in terms of their solution.

Key words:

Regional , health care , medicine , social development , institution , ambulatory and polyclinic , hospital , pharmacy , dispenser , oncological , psychoneurological , endocrinological dispensaries .

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Today, many effective scientific researches in various fields of medicine are conducted in the scientific research institutes and higher education institutions of the developed countries of the world such as USA, Great Britain, Russia, Germany, India, Israel, Egypt. In particular, in Uzbekistan, like developed countries, effective work is being carried out by medical workers in order to protect the health of the population in the field of medicine. It should be noted that in order to develop medicine and the health care system in accordance with world standards, in-depth research and study of the history of this field in our country, especially in local areas and regions, to compare the activity of this field before independence and in the years of independence, and to come to the necessary conclusions is a science today. - is one of the urgent tasks facing the science.

In this article, the medical field in the social development of Navoi region, since 1982, that is, the establishment of Navoi region as part of the Uzbek Soviet Socialist Republic (UzSSR) and the history of health care, like all other fields, about the activities of the government and specialists in the development of the medical field in order to improve the health of the population. opinions are expressed.

On April 20, 1982, with the establishment of Navoi region, the health department of the region was also reorganized. On June 7, 1982, the organizational committee of the Navoi region adopted the decision No. 41, and in its 15th paragraph, the head of the regional health department, I.R. Gulomov, was assigned the task of providing all medical institutions with medical personnel in order to improve the health of the population.

In addition, at the meetings of the executive committee of the Navoi region on October 15, December 16, 1982, at the first meeting of the IV session of the regional council on January 8, 1983, May 20, June 24, the scope of work carried out in the health sector of the region, achievements and shortcomings summarized. For example, on December 27, 1983, at the 8th session of the executive committee of the Navoi region, the activities of the health sector were discussed on the 2nd issue of the agenda. According to it, "...There have been major changes in the healthcare system. By the decision of the regional executive committee, Navoi city hospital, city and district dispensary for skin and venereal diseases were established as part of the regional medical institution. 1 - a sanitary-aviation department, an organizational-methodical department, a nutrition sector, an outpatient clinic and a regional consultation polyclinic were established in the structure of the regional hospital. In addition, as a regional medical institution, there is a sanitary-epidemiological station, a pharmacy department, a medical technical department, a medical farm supply (medhozsnaab), a farm disinfection station, a regional Red Crescent society, oncological, psychoneurological and endocrinological dispensaries, a regional hospital number 2, designed for 120 beds. a medical school, a regional blood transfusion station and a health education center were newly established." [Навоий вилояти давлат архиви. Fund – 1. List – 1. Storage unit No. 187. 97 sheets. 36 – page.]

At that time, the main focus was on the future development of the system of medical institutions in rural areas. In rural areas, 7New

"Ambulance" branches, 9 paramedic stations, and 7 rural medical clinics were established in a short period of time. During this period, a 75-bed "Mother and Child" hospital was opened in Nurota district, a polyclinic for 250 people in Konimekh district, and a dairy kitchen for children (molochnaya kuhnya) for 2500 shares (portions) was opened in Navbahor district. The officials of the regional government constantly focused their attention and energy on newly created medical institutions and the medical requirements of the population. The main attention was paid to issues related to the quality of medical services and the work schedule of institutions. Outpatients and polyclinics have adopted new working hours, their working hours have been extended to 21 hours. Reception of patients was organized in the early morning and on Sundays and holidays. Particular attention was paid to the activity and health of livestock farmers, cotton pickers and workers working in pastures. Based on the recommendation of the commission, a special pre-harvest headquarters was established, and a seminar was organized in order to provide anti-epidemic drugs to the pickers on the basis of medical institutions of Navoi district, in order to exchange experience on preparing for the harvesting process. Chairman of the Executive Committee of Navoi Region, deputy U. In Asatov's report: "Members of the commission went to places during the harvesting process and supervised general pharmacies, disinfection and prevention work there. 560 medical workers and 13 disinfection brigades were organized to provide services to cotton pickers. The aim of all this is to prevent infectious diseases in cotton-growing districts and reduce the indicator of previous years. It is known that high and effective results in improving people's health are provided not by treatment, but by timely preventive measures, as well as mass development of physical activity. Taking this into account, the commission constantly provided for the activities of sports societies. [State archive of Navoi region. Fund – 1. List – 1. Storage unit No. 187. 97 sheets. 37 – p.], we can see the opinions. If we compare the social processes carried out during the period of independence with the social protection carried out in the 80s of the 20th century, we can see a huge difference. As one example, in the report of Deputy U. Asatov at the 8th session of the Executive Council of the Navoi Region held on December 27, 1983, it was noted that "Cultural services to the population within the framework of social

are at a very low level, they are neglected, and veterans of the Great Patriotic War and labor are treated rudely by medical staff." being conspicuous. Construction and commissioning of new buildings of medical institutions in the field of health care is being carried out in a very narrow way. In 1983, the annual plan was fulfilled by 50%." [State archive of Navoi region. Fund – 1. List – 1. Storage unit No. 187. 97 sheets. 37– pp.]. In our opinion, this indicator is a very low indicator compared to the population of the region at that time.

According to the materials stored in the statearchive of Navoi region, it should be noted that in1982-83 special attention was paid to theimplementation of the eleventh five-year plans and thedecisions of the Plenums of May and November 1982. Efforts have been made to create ample conditions forthe production of cotton, grain, agricultural andlivestock products and to perform the tasks of transferto the state, but the sad part is that it is difficult topositively evaluate the attention to the health of thepopulation. Also in the report, "Medical institutions inthe region did not accept the sufficient guidelines forpreventive examination of the population at the end of1983. Unpleasant cases of infectious skin diseases havebeen reported. It is necessary to improve the quality ofmedical examination of the population. Despite efforts, child mortality remains high. It seems that it isnecessary to find a solution to all these shortcomings. We want to clearly include in our work plans for 1984 the issues that are urgent, necessary and important tobe solved. [State archive of Navoi region. Fund – 1. List – 1. Storage unit No. 187. 97 sheets. 37-38 – pages], - opinions are presented. As can be seen from the above sad thoughts, the main attention of the state and government was not on human health, longevity, health of women and girls, healthy growth of babies, infants and young children, but on strengthening production using the power of the population. However, it is worth noting that in some regions of the region, at the end of 1983, there were positive changes in the work done on public health.

In this session, the reports of regional deputiesselected from local areas, for example, if we payattention to the state of health in Navbahor district: Motherhood and childhood protection has always been the

main issue in the focus of health workers of Navbahor district. Maternal mortality has decreased as a result of measures taken in recent years. Large-scale activities for medical examination and rehabilitation of children are being conducted. As a result, infectious diseases have decreased significantly, and medical examination is becoming more important in protecting the health of the population. In 1982, there were many cases of chronic diseases among adults and children in Navoi region. According to archival materials, 3,557 adults and children were registered in the dispensary due to chronic diseases in Navbahor district alone, and received outpatient and inpatient treatment for a year. "Medical workers in the district, with the efforts of local councils, regularly work on promoting medical knowledge, eliminating harmful customs and traditions among the population. In 1982, 1,200 lectures were given by district doctors, and more than 800,000 interviews were conducted by secondary medical personnel. However, despite the achievements, there are still many shortcomings in the field of health care in this region.

Although all conditions are created, the level and quality of medical examination of the population is low. The security of secondary medical, junior service personnel cannot meet modern requirements. The material and technical base of the health sector in the district is not sufficient and it has a negative effect on the population growth. [Fund - 1. List - 1. Storage unit No. 153. 97 sheets. 20 - p.] This was especially noticeable in 1980, when Navbahor district was separated from Navoi district. Instead of 125 standard beds per 10,000 inhabitants, the district has 80 beds. Due to the lack of a building in the district, the department of infectious diseases of the hospital is not established, and the therapeutic department is located 8 km from the Central District Hospital. Most medical facilities are located in adapted rooms, some of them are located in dilapidated and old buildings. [Fund - 1. List - 1. Storage unit No. 153. 97 sheets. 21 - page]. At the end of his speech, the speaker MP asked the Regional Council of People's Deputies to consider solving health issues as the main need of the people of Navbahor district.

During 1983, a wide range of tasks were carried out in the field of health care in the region. During the session of the Regional Council, the next speaker was the deputy A. Khalilova. According to deputy A. Khalilova, "Khatirchi

district has a central hospital with 480 beds, a hospital for infectious diseases with 100 beds, 7 rural outpatient clinics with 125 beds, 52 paramedic and paramedic-obstetric centers, 1 sanitary-epidemiological station and 9 pharmacies. . During the years 1980-82, 3 rural medical clinics and paramedic-midwifery centers were commissioned. The Central Polyclinic was able to receive patients in 22 specialties. And in rural areas, doctors of many specialties are receiving patients." [Fund - 1. List - 1. Storage unit No. 153. 97 sheets. 22 - page.]

"In the villages of Khatirchi district, 2 first aid stations are operating under outpatient clinics. There are 7 directions of a sanitary car with a lift. In addition, children's and midwifery brigades of "Tez zaman" were also established.

Khatirchi district ranks highest in the region in terms of children's education. If we turn to the facts, this indicator was 65.9 in 1981 and 66.4 in 1982. This is very sad." [Fund - 1. List - 1. Storage unit No. 153. 97 sheets. 23 - p.] In our opinion, the lack of doctors and pediatricians was the reason for such a situation in Khatirchi district at that time. Because, if we pay attention to the archival materials, "only 3 out of 7 rural medical clinics are provided with a pediatrician." Supply of medical institutions with pediatricians in the district is 70%." [Fund - 1. List - 1. Storage unit No. 153. 97 sheets. 24 - p.] In addition, at that time, the low level of medical culture among the population, the lack of awareness among parents, and the fact that parents tried to treat young children on their own without turning to medical institutions until they were in serious condition caused disappointments.

Deputy A. Khalilova asked the members of the Council and the regional health department to help provide Khatirchi district with mature, qualified doctors - pediatricians.

Deputy speaker D. Isanov said about the developments in Tomdi district: "As a result of constant care of the party and the government, the cultural life and economy of our population is growing. In our region, a lot of attention is paid to maintaining the health of the population, as a result, people live longer, and the incidence of various diseases decreases. A number of works are being carried out in order to improve the husbandry culture of people living in remote pastures.

Houses, schools, kindergartens are being built with all amenities created by the cooperative in the centers of state farms and farms, and water pipes have been laid on many lands. Now in Tomdi district there is a central hospital with 200 beds, a hospital with five wards with 85 beds, 1 rural medical clinic, 28 paramedic-obstetric centers, a tuberculosis dispensary with 46 beds, a district sanitary-epidemic station, a branch of sanitary aviation, 3 pharmacies, 26 pharmacies points provide medical services to the population. 40 doctors and more than 200 medical workers with secondary education work in these medical institutions. [State archive of Navoi region. Fund - 1. List - 1. Storage unit No. 153. 97 sheets. 15- p.], we can see his opinions. So, when we compare these data with the above data, we can see that the changes are much higher in Tomdi district. As a result of our scientific research, we got such information that at the beginning of 1983, the supply of medical institutions with specialists in Tomdi district was 16.3 doctors and 85.1 medical workers with secondary education per 1000 inhabitants. During this period, 17 types of medical services were regularly provided to the residents of the district. In 1982, the rural medical outpatient clinic located in the state farm named after Lenin in the district was transformed into a 15-bed district hospital, and dental and physiotherapy offices were established in the district hospital of the state farm named after K. Marks.

In 1982, at the meeting of the executive committee of the Navoi region, the issue of "Leading medical services to the population" of the Soviet of People's Deputies of the Tomdi region was considered, several shortcomings were thoroughly discussed, and opinions were expressed on their correction. In the lecture given at the meeting, "Doctors visited shepherd families in remote pastures, monitored their health, and provided appropriate medical care based on the established schedules."

Before the organization of the company, the district party committee determined a number of measures for the organization of this company. These activities are intended to improve the provision of medical services to cattle breeders and to visit them from time to time. Each shepherd's family is provided with a medical kit. The chief specialist staff of the district hospital are in rural district hospitals and paramedic-obstetric centers and provide them with medical assistance and consultation. [State archive of Navoi region. Fund - 1. List - 1. Storage unit No. 153. 97 sheets. 16- pp.].

The above-mentioned facts and processes show that the work carried out in providing medical care to the population cannot be said to be at the level of the demand of that time. In particular, women and children's preventive examination and dispensation were slow. As a result, in 1982, the death rate of children under the age of 1 was higher than that of the region and the Republic. Regarding this topical issue discussed in the session, the speaker said in his report: Due to the size of the territory of Tomdi district, it is difficult to take into account pregnant women in time and conduct interviews, asking the current session of the regional council to provide practical assistance to the issues that they could not solve in order to further improve the provision of medical assistance to pastoralists in Tomdi district and asks for the following: Район марказида 60 ўринли касалхона қурилиши 1981 йилдан буён 17 – трест раҳбарлари айби билан битмай келмоқда. Ушбу қурилишни шу йилга тамомлашга ёрдам берилса;

1. The food funds provided to the district hospital, especially milk 14930 liters, yellow oil 3546 kg, fruit 39 tons, potatoes 8869 kg and other products were not provided in 1982. Even in the first quarter of 1983, we did not receive the funds in full. As a result, the dairy production kitchen is not working. This has a negative impact on the health of mothers and children under one year old. If a leader is appointed to the oblast matlubot society, responsible for the timely delivery of the funds of food provided by the state to Tomdi region;

2. Taking into account the fact that our region is located farthest from the regional center and the lack of medical personnel, in 1983, 10 doctors and 25 medical personnel with secondary education from graduates of institutes and technical schools will be given", [State archive of Navoi region. Fund - 1. List - 1. Storage unit No. 153. 97 sheets. 16- p.] - and asks the session participants to support them.

So, as can be seen from the above points, we cannot say that in the pre-independence period, effective work was carried out to improve the health of the population in the districts and remote villages of the Navoi region. A number of shortcomings in the field of social protection alone in the health sector have been the cause of problems for the population for a long time

without finding their solution . As we mentioned above , after our country gained independence , significant work is being done for the health of the population under the leadership of our country and our President. The fact that about 60 decrees, decisions and orders of the President and about 80 decisions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers were adopted in the next three to four years is a clear proof of this. Currently, on the initiative of President Sh. Mirziyoyev , after studying about 25,000 opinions of the population, based on the noble idea of " For human dignity ", large-scale measures aimed at bringing the healthcare system of our country to a new level and increasing the efficiency and quality of medical services to our people are being implemented .